

FUTURE TEACHERS HAVE PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS CONDITIONS OF SUBSCRIPTION

Toshtemirova Nasibakhan

Andijan State University

Teacher of the "General Pedagogy" department

ANNOTATION. This article discusses the content of future teachers' pedagogical skills and the requirements for a skilled pedagogue.

Key words: pedagogical ability, pedagogical technique, society's requirements, pedagogical skill, high-level culture, national pedagogy, national values, owner of moral soul, ideological treasure, professional activity.

INTRODUCTION. A teacher is a person with a very high level of culture. He needs to know a lot. Nowadays, he should be aware of the achievements and news in the field of science he is studying. In order to teach students daily activities, he should regularly study, learn, fill and deepen his knowledge. So, the main thing of a pedagogue, pedagogic skill is independent study. It is clear to everyone that after the independence of Uzbekistan, there were great changes in the field of education, in terms of restoration of national morals, and in terms of the further development of national values. It should not be forgotten that the great future of the state is young people who have deep knowledge and pure morals. Pedagogical skill is not an innate or hereditary trait, but a product of research and creative work. At the core of this multifaceted pedagogical activity is creative work. If we look at the professional skills program of the pedagogue in practice, then the first place is its integral quality-skills.

The content of the concept of teacher's pedagogical skills can be explained

as follows:

1. A high level of culture, a high indicator of knowledge and intelligence.
2. He has excellent knowledge of his subject.
3. Thorough mastery of knowledge in the fields of pedagogy and psychology, and ability to use them in professional activities.
4. Perfect knowledge of educational methods.

Pedagogical skill system is the following interrelated main consists of components:

1. Obedience to the requirements of pedagogical humanitarianism.
2. Perfect knowledge of professional knowledge in connection with other disciplines.
3. Having pedagogical skills.
4. Mastering the secrets of pedagogical techniques.

Among all professions, the teaching profession has a special and important social importance. After all, the teacher is the architect of the maturity of the soul of the young generation, a person who gives education and training to young people. Today, he trains young people ideologically and politically, teaches them the laws of nature, society, social life, development of thinking, prepares young people for work, helps them master the secrets of professions and social-economic situations that are important for society. solves. This responsibility requires the teacher to be a skilled master of his profession, to have an educational impact on the students, and to develop their interest, ability, talent, faith and practical skills in every way. It requires a professional to find them.

To do this, constantly improve the professional skills, skills and qualifications of teachers, take care of them in every way, create the necessary conditions, provide necessary material, scientific-methodical and technical support, creative teachers' it is necessary to help to regularly increase initiative.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. In the higher

education of pedagogy, the process of adaptation to education is carried out with the help of staff serving future teachers, elements of the material base and many other tools. A perfect pedagogical system was created by Jan Amos Comenius. Relying on the advanced ideas of his time, he made a call to teach everyone everything. His great treatise "Great Didactics" is one of the first works of theoretical pedagogy.

J.J. Rousseau (1712-1858), (I.G. Pestolotsy, A. Destervenrg, R. Owen (17711-1858), A.N. Radishchev (1749-1802), V.G. Belinsky, A. Gersen, I.I. Pirogov, N.G. Chernishevsky (1822-1899), the services of N.D. Dobrolyubov are great. K.D. Ushinsky made a great contribution to the development of the theory of pedagogy. He is called the father of Russian pedagogy. It is considered an indispensable condition for any discipline to stand out and function normally. .

RESULTS. Pedagogy teaches that the purpose of education changes depending on the requirements of society and the age characteristics of students. Reveals the components of education and the connections between them. Based on this, it summarizes the experiences in the field of education and shows the prospects and ways of the future development of education. Today, in the period of independence, in the spirit of the ideas of independence, the time has come to restore the ancient folk tradition, to use rich and colorful folk pedagogy in education. Genres such as epics, fairy tales, lappar, proverbs, quick sayings, and riddles, which have not lost their essence in the work of modern education, are of great importance in the education of the young generation in the period of independence.

The ability of a teacher to analyze himself in having professional competence

is considered significant. Self-analysis in professional activity by a pedagogue

is the study of the nature of their practical actions. Himself

through analysis, the pedagogue will have the opportunity to objectively evaluate himself. After all, it is important for pedagogues to have the qualities of professional competence that they have the skills of self-assessment. Self-evaluation (SEO) is a person's self-evaluation through self-analysis. Self-assessment provides the subject with an assessment of his personal capabilities, an objective assessment of himself, and self-satisfaction. Self-assessment should help a person to reveal his abilities on his own. Self-assessment is difficult, but a person can be directly trained for it. As with any specialist, a number of factors affect the pedagogue's ability to evaluate himself effectively.

DISCUSSION. Pedagogical profession is individual in its essence. The vital role of every pedagogue is to be a master of his work, a master is expressed as very advanced, knowledgeable or skillfully performing his work. Pedagogical skills are visible in his work. First of all, a pedagogue should be well versed in the laws and mechanisms of the pedagogical process. In this sense, the general skills of the pedagogue and his pedagogical technique are of great importance. Skill is a special power. It is impossible to become a master at a high or low level. Mastery may or may not be attained. A real master is beautiful only during his work. Achieving pedagogical skills is achieved with certain personal qualities of the pedagogue. Pedagogical skill represents the development of pedagogical activities, acquisition of pedagogical techniques, as well as the personality of the pedagogue, his experience, civil and professional status. Pedagogical skill as a category has its own scientific basis. The scientific approaches of recent years have made it possible to draw the following conclusion in relation to this situation: pedagogical skill is understood as a bright manifestation of individuality in professional activity.

CONCLUSION. Despite the fact that there are so many definitions of pedagogical skill, some aspects of skill are definitely expressed in them.

Pedagogy is an honorable but very difficult profession. To be good, it is not enough to master pedagogical theory. Because in the pedagogical theory, the general laws and rules of teaching and upbringing of children, generalized methodical ideas are stated, attention to the individual characteristics of young people is emphasized. Preschool education life is a small pedagogical process and is very diverse. There are situations that do not correspond to the pedagogical theory.

This requires extensive knowledge, thorough practical training, high pedagogical skills and creativity from the pedagogue.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmedzhanov M.M., Khojaev B.Q., Hasanova Z.D. Pedagogical skills - Bukhara

State University, 2014

2. G.I. Khasanova "Advantages of using customized teaching technology in the educational process" Jizzakh: 2020. 420 pages. 223-225b

3. Manzura, N. (2021). Sustainable Activity in the Teaching Profession and Its

Foundations. Journal of Psychology and Education, 58(2), 1339-1345

4. Abdurakhmonovna, N. M. (2021). Pedagogical and Psychological Aspects of

Professional Sustainability of Future Teachers.

5. Content of developing the creative abilities of teachers of higher education

institutions. Khasanova Gulnoza Ilhomovna

6. Norquziyeva, M. (2021). Spiritual and moral education of students based on folklore: spiritual and moral education of students based on folklore. Journal of preschool education, 2(2). izvlecheno noun

<https://presedu.jspi.uz/index.php/presedu/article/view/832>

7. Vygotsky L.S. Pedagogical psychology. - M.: "Pedagogy", 1999. -S. 321.

8. Abdurakhmanova R.B. Stanovlenie professionalnoy napravlenosti pedagog and psychologist Autoref. dis. sugar psycho. science – Tashkent, 2005.-22 p

"A specialist who is a skilled master of his profession, highly cultured, has a deep knowledge of his subject, is able to analyze the fields of related sciences well, and has mastered the methods of education and training perfectly." Based on the essence of this definition, the content of the concept of teacher's pedagogical skills can be explained as follows:

1. A high level of culture, a high indicator of knowledge and intelligence.
2. He has excellent knowledge of his subject.
3. Thorough mastery of knowledge in the field of pedagogy and psychology, among them

be able to use it in professional activities.

4. Excellent knowledge of the methodology of educational work.

Pedagogical skill system is the following interrelated main consists of components:

1. Obedience to the requirements of pedagogical humanitarianism.
2. Perfect knowledge of professional knowledge in connection with other disciplines.
3. Having pedagogical skills.
4. Mastering the secrets of pedagogical techniques.

Among all professions, the teaching profession has a special and important social importance.

After all, the teacher is the architect of the maturity of the soul of the young generation, a person who gives education and training to young people. Today,

he trains young people ideologically and politically, teaches them the laws of nature, society, social life, development of thinking, prepares young people for work, helps them master the secrets of professions and social-economic situations that are important for society. solves. This is the responsibility of the teacher to be a master of his profession, to teach the students educational

It requires a professional to influence and find ways to develop their interests, abilities, talents, beliefs and practical skills in a comprehensive way.

To do this, constantly improve the professional skills, skills and qualifications of teachers, take care of them in every way, create the necessary conditions, provide necessary material, scientific-methodical and technical support, creative teachers' it is necessary to help to regularly increase initiative.

Based on this, the science of "Pedagogical skill" serves to train skilled teachers, it is a science that teaches the secrets and skill of professional activity of teachers and educators and provides information about its improvement. learns the essence of pedagogical skills in teachers, the ways, means, and forms of developing their professional activities within the requirements of the present time.

mutual cooperation, communication tactics, speech culture, thinking, organization and implementation of the educator's spiritual-educational and educational work, in this process it teaches the features of being able to control behavior and emotions, and one's own profession provides information about the system of developing pedagogical activities. Pedagogical skills are improved during the pedagogical activities of teachers.

Pedagogical activity is the labor activity of specially trained teachers who are accountable to the society and the state in order to prepare the young generation for life and work. Future teachers should know the following components of activity in the course of their pedagogical activities:

The purpose of pedagogical activity.

- Object and subject of pedagogical activity.
- Tool of pedagogical activity.

A teacher who does not understand the essence of the pedagogical process and does not have deep respect for the child will not have an idea that ensures the effectiveness of education and human development. The task of the pedagogical process is to impart knowledge, educate, and develop, and determines the criteria of teachers' activity. The activity of teachers is a means of action of the pedagogical process. To the subject of the pedagogical process, to the person being educated, to the student and group of students, and to the individual student, the subjects of the pedagogical process are parents,

teachers, educators, class team, pedagogical team are responsible and they carry out education and upbringing activities based on the requirements of the society. A teacher's achievement of positive results in his pedagogical activity is determined by how well he can apply his professional skills, i.e. acquired knowledge, in his life and practical activities. The system of abilities necessary for effective pedagogical activity of teachers: knowledge, ability to understand the child, observation, speech skills, organization, ability to see the future, distribution of attention, correct assessment of the situation, emergence timely elimination of all kinds of possible conflicts, making students interested in learning.

In order to solve the tasks and tasks related to the profession from the content of this science, to manage the educational process, to approach it from the point of view of pedagogic-psychological teaching, to model education in the spirit of our national traditions based on modern methods, - information on the necessity of teacher skills and systems of their improvement for the implementation of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process are included.

Accordingly, the subject of "Pedagogical skills" is aimed at forming professional knowledge and abilities in teachers, educating creativity, acquiring skills, abilities and qualifications, teaching about pedagogical technique, pedagogical cooperation, pedagogical politeness, speech culture. gives information.